

A study to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding selected emergency cardiac medications among ICU staff in a selected hospital

¹Ms. Mayuri Madhukar Baikar, ²Mr. Krunal Malkapure, ³Ms. Reshma Ansari
Clinical instructor,
Rastrasant Janardhan College of Nursing, Kopargaon, Ahmednagar-423601

Corresponding Author:
Ms. Mayuri Madhukar Baikar
Clinical instructor,
Rastrasant Janardhan College of Nursing, Kopargaon, Ahmednagar-423601

Address:
Shirdi
Ahmednagar(Dist), Maharastra (State)

ABSTRACT

Background: Heart attacks and strokes are usually acute events and are mainly caused by a blockage that prevents blood from flowing to the heart or brain. Drug treatment of hypertension, diabetes and high blood lipids are necessary to reduce cardiovascular risk and prevent heart attacks and strokes among people with these conditions.

Materials and methods: The research approach adopted for the study was one group pre-test and post-test experimental design. The study comprises of 30 nurses of selected Hospital who fulfilled inclusive criteria selected by Convenient Sampling method. Knowledge questionnaire was used for data collection. The content Validity of the tool was established in consultation with guide and 12 experts from the field of Medical Surgical Nursing. Reliability coefficient of knowledge questionnaire was calculated using Carl Pearson Coefficient of Correlation. Formal permission was obtained from concerned authority from selected hospital for data collection. Data were tabulated and analyzed.

Results: . The study revealed that the mean score among nurses was 15(46%) during pre test rose up to 24(77.60%) in the post test evaluation. Result interpreted that there was a significant increase in knowledge level of nurses after administration of structured teaching program. It is evident that the calculated 't' value was greater than the table value of 't' at 0.05 level. This indicates that planned teaching was effective in improving the knowledge of the nurses. The study also revealed that there is a significant association between demographic characteristics, such as total years of professional experience, years of experience in current position with the knowledge score.

Conclusion: The study was done to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding selected emergency cardiac medications among ICU staff. The result of this study shows that the most of the nurses had excellent knowledge after administration of structured teaching program. The study also revealed that there is a significant association between demographic characteristics such as total years of professional experience, years of experience in current position with the knowledge score. This study will help the nurse to develop appropriate teaching material to improve knowledge regarding emergency cardiac medication.

Key Words: structured teaching program, knowledge, cardiac medication

INTRODUCTION

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are the leading cause of death globally. An estimated 17.9 million people died from CVDs in 2019, representing 32% of all global deaths. Of these deaths, 85% were due to heart attack and stroke. Over three quarters of CVD deaths take place in low- and middle-income countries. Out of the 17 million premature deaths (under the age of 70) due to non-communicable diseases in 2019, 38% were caused by CVDs. Most cardiovascular diseases can be prevented by addressing behavioral risk factors such as tobacco use, unhealthy diet and obesity, physical inactivity and harmful use of alcohol. It is important to detect cardiovascular disease as early as possible so that management with counselling and medicines can begin.¹

cardiovascular disease reduction lies in the inclusion of cardiovascular disease management interventions in universal health coverage packages, although in a high number of countries health systems require significant investment and reorientation to effectively manage CVDs.¹

Evidence from 18 countries has shown that hypertension programmes can be implemented efficiently and cost-effectively at the primary care level which will ultimately result in reduced coronary heart disease and stroke. Patients with cardiovascular disease should have access to appropriate technology and medication. Basic

medicines that should be available include aspirin, beta-blockers, angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors and, statins. An acute event such as a heart attack or stroke should be promptly managed. Sometimes, surgical operations are required to treat CVDs. coronary artery bypass, balloon angioplasty (where a small balloon-like device is threaded through an artery to open the blockage), valve repair and replacement, heart transplantation and artificial heart operations. Medical devices are required to treat some CVDs. Such devices include pacemakers, prosthetic valves, and patches for closing holes in the heart. Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are a group of disorders of the heart and blood vessels. They include coronary heart disease a disease of the blood vessels supplying the heart muscle, cerebrovascular disease a disease of the blood vessels supplying the brain, peripheral arterial disease a disease of blood vessels supplying the arms and legs, rheumatic heart disease damage to the heart muscle and heart valves from rheumatic fever, caused by streptococcal bacteria, congenital heart disease birth defects that affect the normal development and functioning of the heart caused by malformations of the heart structure from birth and deep vein thrombosis and pulmonary embolism – blood clots in the leg veins, which can dislodge and move to the heart and lungs.¹

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are a group of disorders of the heart and blood vessels. coronary heart disease a disease of the blood vessels supplying the heart muscle; cerebro vascular disease a disease of the blood vessels supplying the brain; peripheral arterial disease a disease of blood vessels supplying the arms and legs rheumatic heart disease damage to the heart muscle and heart valves from rheumatic fever, caused by streptococcal bacteria congenital heart disease birth defects that affect the normal development and functioning of the heart caused by malformations of the heart structure from birth; and deep vein thrombosis and pulmonary embolism – blood clots in the leg veins, which can dislodge and move to the heart and lungs. Heart attacks and strokes are usually acute events and are mainly caused by a blockage that prevents blood from flowing to the heart or brain. The most common reason for this is a build-up of fatty deposits on the inner walls of the blood vessels that supply the heart or brain. Strokes can be caused by bleeding from a blood vessel in the brain or from blood clots.¹

Often, there are no symptoms of the underlying disease of the blood vessels. A heart attack or stroke may be the first sign of underlying disease pain or discomfort in the centre of the chest; and/or pain or discomfort in the arms, the left shoulder, elbows, jaw, or back. In addition the person may experience difficulty in breathing or shortness of breath; nausea or vomiting; light-headedness or faintness; a cold sweat; and turning pale. Women are more likely than men to have shortness of breath, nausea, vomiting, and back or jaw pain. The most common symptom of a stroke is sudden weakness of the face, arm, or leg, most often on one side of the body numbness of the face, arm, or leg, especially on one side of the body confusion, difficulty speaking or understanding speech difficulty seeing with one or both eyes difficulty walking, dizziness and/or loss of balance or coordination; severe headache with no known cause; and/or fainting or unconsciousness.¹

Heart disease occurs when the blood vessels of your heart are damaged or diseased. This leads to fatty deposit buildups called plaque, which can block the blood vessels or lead to blood clots. Heart disease can cause many

serious health problems such as heart attack, congestive heart failure, or heart rhythm problems. All of these health issues can result in death, so treating heart disease is important. To treat your heart disease, your doctor will probably recommend that you make important lifestyle changes, such as starting an exercise program. They'll also likely prescribe medications. Many types of medications are available and they help treat heart disease in different ways.²

Your medication treatment plan will depend on how heart disease affects your cardiovascular system, meaning your heart and blood vessels. Not all heart disease is the same, so it's not all treated the same way. For instance, your heart disease may cause excessive blood clotting, or it may increase your blood pressure, or it could do both. As a result, you may need more than one medication to manage your heart disease symptoms. ACE inhibitors prevent your body from forming angiotensin. Angiotensin is a hormone that causes your blood vessels to constrict or get smaller, which increases your blood pressure. Lower angiotensin levels, then, help widen your blood vessels and let your blood flow more easily. This reduces your blood pressure. Your doctor may prescribe an ACE inhibitor if you have high blood pressure or heart failure. They may also prescribe one after you've had a heart attack. These drugs can help your heart muscle recover from the lack of oxygen during the attack. They can also help prevent another heart attack.²

ARBs block the effects of angiotensin on your heart. This effect lowers your blood pressure. Your doctor may prescribe an ARB if you have high blood pressure or congestive heart failure. Like ACE inhibitors, ARBs can help you recover after a heart attack. losartan (Cozaar) olmesartan (Benicar) valsartan (Diovan) Anticoagulants Your doctor may prescribe an anticoagulant to prevent heart attack, stroke, or other serious health problems. With heart disease, one of the main problems is plaque. A buildup of plaque in a blood vessel can lead to a blood clot, which can cause serious problems when it breaks free of the plaque. For instance, if the clot gets lodged in a heart vessel, it can partly or completely block blood flow to the heart and cause a heart attack. If the blood clot travels to the lungs, a pulmonary embolism could result. And if a clot lodges in the brain, a stroke could occur. Anticoagulants work by preventing blood clots from forming. Some do this by preventing your body from making substances called clotting factors. Others keep the clotting factors from working or prevent other chemicals from forming so that clots can't develop. Anticoagulants don't break up existing blood clots, however. enoxaparin (Lovenox), heparin, warfarin (Coumadin)²

Antiplatelet agents Your doctor may prescribe an antiplatelet drug to prevent a future heart attack if you've already had one or if you have plaque buildup in your arteries. They may also prescribe one if you have an abnormal heart rhythm, such as atrial fibrillation. Arrhythmias raise your risk of blood clots. Like anticoagulants, antiplatelet medications help prevent blood clots, but they do so in a different way. They prevent your body from making a substance, called thromboxane, that tells platelets to stick together to form a clot. Aspirin, clopidogrel (Plavix), prasugrel (Effient) Beta-blockers are a broad category of medications used to treat different problems from heart disease. In general, beta-blockers work by blocking the actions of certain chemicals that stimulate your heart, such as epinephrine (adrenaline). This allows the heart to beat more slowly

and less forcefully. Your doctor may prescribe a beta-blocker to help prevent a first heart attack as well as repeat heart attacks. They may also prescribe one if you have high blood pressure, heart failure, chest pain, or an arrhythmia. metoprolol (Lopressor) , labetalol (Trandate), propranolol (Inderal) Calcium is needed for all muscles to move, including the heart. Calcium channel blockers work by regulating the amount of calcium that enters muscle cells in your heart and blood vessels. This makes your heart beat less forcefully and helps blood vessels relax.²

Your doctor may prescribe a calcium channel blocker if you have high blood pressure, chest pain, or a heart arrhythmia. amlodipine (Norvasc), diltiazem (Cardizem), nifedipine (Procardia) High cholesterol levels in your blood can cause plaque to build up. This can lead to narrowed or blocked blood vessels that can cause heart attack, stroke, or other serious problems. Cholesterol medications help lower your levels of LDL or “bad” cholesterol and raise your levels of HDL or “good” cholesterol. These steps lower your risk of plaque buildup. Some cholesterol drugs have been proven to decrease the risk of death from heart disease. statins such as atorvastatin (Lipitor), pravastatin sodium (Pravachol), and simvastatin (Zocor), bile acid resins such as cholestyramine, cholesterol absorption inhibitors such as ezetimibe (Zetia), fibric acid derivatives such as fenofibrate (Tricor) nicotinic acid such as niacin (Niacor) and Digitalis medication is available as digoxin (Lanoxin). It increases the amount of calcium in the cells of your heart. This makes your heart pump harder, sending out more blood with each beat. For this reason, your doctor may prescribe digitalis medication if you have heart failure. Digitalis medication also works by slowing certain electrical signals sent within your heart. This reduces the total number of signals, which helps reduce arrhythmias. Your doctor may also prescribe digitalis if you have an irregular heart rhythm such as atrial fibrillation. Digoxin is often prescribed in combination with diuretics and an ACE inhibitor. Nitrates work by widening your blood vessels so blood can pass through more easily. Your doctor may prescribe a nitrate if you have angina (chest pain) or heart failure. nitroglycerin (Nitrostat, Nitro-Dur), isosorbide dinitrate (Isordil), isosorbide mononitrate (Monoket).²

Problem Statement

“A study to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding selected emergency cardiac medications among ICU staff in a selected hospital.”

Objectives of the Study

1. To assess the knowledge level of ICU staff regarding selected emergency cardiac medications
2. To assess the effectiveness of structured teaching program on knowledge regarding selected emergency cardiac medication among ICU staff
3. To find out the association between the Knowledge Regarding Selected Emergency Cardiac Medications with selected demographic variable
- 4.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials and methods: The research approach adopted for the study was one group pre-test and post-test quasi experimental design. The study comprises of 40 nurses of selected Hospital who fulfilled inclusive criteria selected by Convenient Sampling method. Knowledge questionnaire was used for data collection. The content Validity of the tool was established in consultation with guide and 12 experts from the field of Medical Surgical Nursing. Reliability coefficient of knowledge questionnaire was calculated using Carl Pearson Coefficient of Correlation. . The items were coded and the reliability was calculated. The reliability co-efficient was found to be 0.83 which indicated that tool was reliable. Formal permission was obtained from concerned authority from selected hospital for data collection.

Hypotheses

- **H₁**- There is significant relationship with Knowledge Regarding Selected Emergency Cardiac Medications Among ICU Staff
- **H₂**-There is significance association between pre test Knowledge score Regarding Selected Emergency Cardiac Medications Among ICU Staff with their association demographic variable.

RESULTS:

Analysis and interpretation is based on the objectives of the study. The analysis was done with the help of inferential and descriptive statistics.

Section A:-Description of socio- demographic characteristic of ICU nursing staffs

Table 1: Percentage wise distribution of nurses according to their demographic characteristics.

Table No-I

n=30

Sr.No	Demographic variables		Frequency	%
1	Age	20-25 yr	4	15
		26-30 yr	9	30
		31- 35 yr	11	35
		36-40 years	6	20
		Total	30	100
2	Gender	Male	12	40
		Female	18	60
		Total	30	100
3	Qualification	GNM	13	45
		BSC (N)	11	35
		MSc(N)	6	20
		DCN/ PBCN	00	00
		Total	30	100
4	Total period of professional experience	1-2 yr	11	36
		3-4 yr	7	24
		5-6 yr	10	32
		7-8 yr	2	08
		Total	30	100

5	Total year of ICU/ CCU Experience	1-2 yr	6	20
		3-4 yr	4	14
		5-6 yr	14	46
		7-8 yr	6	20
		Total	30	100
6	ACLS Training	Attended	19	65
		Not Attended	11	35
		Total	30	100
7	Any conference and workshop related to cardiac	Attended	10	33
		Not Attended	20	67
		Total	30	100

Section B :

1. To assess the knowledge level of ICU staff regarding selected emergency cardiac medications

Assessment of knowledge regarding selected emergency cardiac medication among nursing staff**Table No . II****n=30**

SN	Knowledge area	Max score	Pretest Score	
			Mean	SD
1	Knowledge regarding selected emergency cardiac medication	15	8.12	2.22

Section II: The assessment of nurses' knowledge regarding prevention of surgical site infection.

Fig: 1 reveals that there is a major difference in the pre and post test scores and therefore it can be understood that a teaching programme can improve nurses' knowledge.

Level Of Knowledge Score	Pre test		Post test	
	f	%	f	%
Poor	2	5	0	0
Average	32	80	0	0
Good	6	15	13	32.5
Excellent	0	0	27	67.5

Section: C

2. To assess the effectiveness of structured teaching program on knowledge regarding selected emergency cardiac medication among ICU staff

Area wise comparison of mean, SD, of pre-test and post test knowledge selective emergency cardiac medication

Part I Overall Area wise comparison of mean, SD of pretest and posttest knowledge score area

Table No. III**n=30**

S N	Knowledge area	Max. score	Pretest score		Post test score	
			Mean	SD	Mean	SD
1	Knowledge regarding selected emergency cardiac medication	15	8.12	2.22	11.02	3.15

Section III: Effectiveness of teaching program regarding prevention of surgical site infection among nurses.

The table compares the pre and post test knowledge. It is seen that the mean score was 15 during pre test rose up to 24 in the post test evaluation. Therefore the effectiveness of the study is proven.

Table 2: Effectiveness of teaching program regarding prevention of surgical site infection

N=40

Knowledge score	Maximum score	Mean	Standard deviation	Mean percentage	t-value	p-value
Pre Test	15	10.50	2.20	42.00	27.81	0.000 S, $p < 0.05$
Post Test	24	19.40	1.90	77.60		

Section IV: Association of Knowledge Score with Demographic Variables

The table 3 describes that, the demographic characteristics, such as total years of professional experience, years of experience in current position was statistically significant ie, there is association with the post-test level of knowledge regarding prevention of surgical site infection.

Table.3 Association of Knowledge Score In Relation To Demographic Variables

Demographic Variables	No. of Nurses	Mean knowledge score	F-value	p-value
Age(yrs)				
20-25 years	6	20 \pm 1.83	1.37	0.2675 NS, $P > 0.05$
26-30years	19	18.95 \pm 1.90		
31-35 years	13	19.46 \pm 1.69		
Above 35 years	2	21.5 \pm 1.5		
Professional qualification				
RGNM (Diploma)	32	19.03 \pm 1.86	6.67	0.2267 NS, $P > 0.05$
BSc Nursing (Degree)	8	20.88 \pm 1.55		
Total years of professional experience				
0 to 3year	9	18.77 \pm 1.75	3.36	0.0292 S, $P < 0.05$
4 to 7years	19	18.84 \pm 1.72		
8 to 11 years	11	20.81 \pm 1.64		
12 years or more	1	20 \pm 0		
Duration of employment in current Position.				
0 to 2 year	17	18.76 \pm 2.19	1.16	0.034 S, $P < 0.05$
3 to 5years	21	19.81 \pm 1.82		
6 to 8 years	2	20.5 \pm 0.5		
9 years or more	0	0 \pm 0		
Exposure to in-service education				

Yes	16	20.56± 1.71	12.49	0.1901
No	24	18.62± 1.69		
Source of information				
Mass media	15	19.80±1.83	0.58	0.564
As a part of curriculum	12	19.00±1.14		
Books and journals	13	19.31±2.27		

DISCUSSION

The present study was carried out among 30 nurses to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching program regarding the knowledge on emergency cardiac medication.

A structured teaching programme was administered to the subjects. The present study assessed the knowledge of nurses regarding prevention of emergency cardiac medication before administration of structured teaching program and found that maximum number of patients 22 (80%) had average knowledge, 6 (15%) had good knowledge, remaining 2 (5%) had a poor knowledge. None of the subjects found to have excellent knowledge. After the structured teaching programme the post-test showed that the maximum number of samples 17 (67.5%) had excellent knowledge, 13 (32.5%) had gained good knowledge and none of the sample had inadequate knowledge.

The comparison of pre-test knowledge scores and post-test knowledge scores of the subjects shows that the overall mean in the pre-test was 10.50 with SD 2.20 and in the post-test 19.40 with SD 1.90. The overall improvement mean was 8.9 with 't'- value 27.81 which was highly significant at $P>0.05$ level. This showed that there was a significant improvement in knowledge of staff nurses after the structured teaching programme.

The study also revealed that the association of knowledge score with demographic characteristics, such as total years of professional experience, years of experience in current position was statistically significant.

CONCLUSION

The study was conducted among nurses to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching program regarding the knowledge on emergency cardiac medication. The study revealed that a structured teaching may increase the knowledge of nurses regarding an emergency cardiac medication. Improper management and caring of cardiac patient will lead to many complications and may even cause death. Improving knowledge among staff nurses is a vital component of an emergency cardiac medication.

Reference

1. World Health Organization. (n.d.). Cardiovascular diseases (cvds). World Health Organization. Retrieved January 28, 2022, from [https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/cardiovascular-diseases-\(cvds\)](https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/cardiovascular-diseases-(cvds))
2. Donovan, R. (2020, February 1). Heart disease drugs: What they are and what they do. Healthline. Retrieved January 28, 2022, from <https://www.healthline.com/health/heart-disease/drugs#takeaway>
3. World Health Organization. (n.d.). Cardiovascular diseases (cvds). World Health Organization. Retrieved January 28, 2022, from [https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/cardiovascular-diseases-\(cvds\)](https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/cardiovascular-diseases-(cvds))
4. World Health Organization. (n.d.). Cardiovascular diseases (cvds). World Health Organization. Retrieved January 28, 2022, from [https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/cardiovascular-diseases-\(cvds\)](https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/cardiovascular-diseases-(cvds))
5. Dorairaj Prabhakaran, Panniyammakal Jeemon, Ambuj Roy Cardiovascular Diseases in India Current Epidemiology and Future Directions *Circulation*. 2016;133:1605–1620 Originally published 19 Apr 2016 <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.114.008729>
6. Mumbai hospitals witness 50% rise in emergency footfall of patients with heart attacks. *Hindustan Times*. (2021, September 28). Retrieved January 28, 2022, from <https://www.hindustantimes.com/cities/mumbai-news/mumbai-hospitals-witness-50-rise-in-emergency-footfall-of-patients-with-heart-attacks-101632852542639.html>
7. World Health Organization. (n.d.). Cardiovascular diseases (cvds). World Health Organization. Retrieved January 28, 2022, from [https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/cardiovascular-diseases-\(cvds\)](https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/cardiovascular-diseases-(cvds))
8. Assess verb - definition, pictures, pronunciation and usage notes: Oxford Advanced American Dictionary at [Oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com](http://oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com).
9. Effectiveness. effectiveness noun - Definition, pictures, pronunciation and usage notes | Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary at OxfordLearnersDictionaries.com. (n.d.). Retrieved January 29, 2022, from <https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/>
10. Bimelkottarathil Follow. (n.d.). Collins. SlideShare. Retrieved January 29, 2022, from <https://www.slideshare.net/bimelk/collins->
11. Knowledge. knowledge noun - Definition, pictures, pronunciation and usage notes | Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary at OxfordLearnersDictionaries.com
12. Encyclopædia Britannica, inc. (n.d.). Cardiovascular drug. Encyclopædia Britannica. Retrieved January 29, 2022, from <https://www.britannica.com/science/cardiovascular-drug>
13. Intensive-care noun - definition, pictures, pronunciation and usage notes: Oxford Advanced American Dictionary at Oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com.
14. Thokchom lilabati devi a study to assess the effect of planned teaching programme on knowledge regarding emergency drug administration among b.sc nursing students in selected nursing college of guwahati, assam international journal of scientific research volume - 10 | issue - 04 | april - 2021 | print issn no. 2277 - 8179 | doi : 10.36106/ijsr
15. Upendrababu, V., Sweta, Lorenz, U. P., (2018). Effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding selected emergency cardiac medications among 3rd year B. SC nursing students. *Asian Journal of Nursing Education and Research*, 8(4), 462. <https://doi.org/10.5958/2349-2996.2018.00093.9>
16. Mr. Rajendra D. Lamkhede Effectiveness of planned teaching programme on knowledge of emergency drugs among staff nurses *Sinhgadh e Journal of Nursing*, Vol. IV, Issue I, June 2014.
17. ArchalaKhemnar, Manisha Karkar and Yevandge Nagin An experimental study to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding utilization of crash cart in hospitals among 4 th year b.sc nursing students of selected nursing colleges in Pune city *International Journal of Applied Research* 2017; 3(7): 469-473
18. Jenifer, D (2014) A Study to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on anticoagulant drug compliance among patients with mechanical heart valve in GKNM Hospital, Coimbatore. Masters thesis, G.Kuppusawamy Naidu Memorial Hospital, Coimbatore.

19. Effectiveness of teaching program on Critical Care Nurses performance regarding emergency cart in Intensive Care Units. (2018). *Assiut Scientific Nursing Journal*, 6(14.1), 94–101. <https://doi.org/10.21608/asnj.2018.59752>
20. Stiji, Samuel (2016) Effectiveness of planned teaching programme on the knowledge and practice regarding infection control measures for postoperative cardiac patients among staff nurses at a selected hospital, Chennai. Masters thesis, MMM College of Nursing, Chennai.
21. Abdulrdha Mustafa Flayyih, Mansour Kalida Alwan Effectiveness of an Instructional Program on Nurse's Knowledge and practice concerning Patients Discharge Planning post Cardiac Surgery at Cardiac Centers and hospitals in Baghdad city *Asian Journal of Nursing Education and Research* Year : 2019, Volume : 9, Issue : 1 First page : (35) Last page : (42)
22. Karthika, M (2018) Effectiveness of Emergency Preparedness Protocol on knowledge and skill regarding pre hospital management of cardiac emergencies among patients with chronic illness and their caregivers at selected hospitals, Chennai. Masters thesis, Omayal Achi College of Nursing, Chennai.
23. Choudhry, N. K., Avorn, J., Glynn, R. J., Antman, E. M., (2011). Full coverage for preventive medications after myocardial infarction. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 365(22), 2088–2097. <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejmsa1107913>
24. Michael W. Rich, Heart failure disease management: a critical review, *Journal of Cardiac Failure*, Volume 5, Issue 1,1999, Pages 64-75, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1071-9164\(99\)90026-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1071-9164(99)90026-X).
25. Yancy, C. W., Januzzi, J. L., Allen, L. A., Butler, J.. (2018). 2017 ACC expert consensus decision pathway for optimization of heart failure treatment: Answers to 10 pivotal issues about heart failure with reduced ejection fraction. *Journal of the American College of Cardiology*, 71(2), 201–230. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jacc.2017.11.025>
26. Lucas, F. L., DeLorenzo, M. A., Siewers, A. E., & Wennberg, D. E. (2006). Temporal trends in the utilization of diagnostic testing and treatments for cardiovascular disease in the United States, 1993–2001. *Circulation*, 113(3), 374–379. <https://doi.org/10.1161/circulationaha.105.560433>
27. Sug Yoon, S., Heller, R. F., Levi, C., Wiggers, J., & Fitzgerald, P. E. (2001). Knowledge of stroke risk factors, warning symptoms, and treatment among an Australian urban population. *Stroke*, 32(8), 1926–1930. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.str.32.8.1926>
28. Summerfield, N, & Pace, C. (2021). Emergency cardiac pharmacology for nurses. *The Veterinary Nurse*, 12(3), 146–151. <https://doi.org/10.12968/vetn.2021.12.3.146>
29. Mei-Jung Chen, Shu Yu, I-Ju Chen, Kai-Wei K. Wang, Evaluation of nurses' knowledge and understanding of obstacles encountered when administering resuscitation medications, *Nurse Education Today*, Volume 34, Issue 2, 2014, Pages 177-184, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2013.04.011>.
30. Carol J. Hope, PHARM.D., M.S., Jingwei Wu, M.S., Wanzhu Tu, PH.D., James Young, PHARM.D., Michael D. Murray, PHARM.D., M.P.H., Association of medication adherence, knowledge, and skills with emergency department visits by adults 50 years or older with congestive heart failure, *American Journal of Health-System Pharmacy*, Volume 61, Issue 19, 1 October 2004, Pages 2043–2049, <https://doi.org/10.1093/ajhp/61.19.2043>
31. Elizabeth Manias, Shane Bullock, The educational preparation of undergraduate nursing students in pharmacology: clinical nurses' perceptions and experiences of graduate nurses' medication knowledge, *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, Volume 39, Issue 8, 2002, Pages 773-784, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0020-7489\(02\)00008-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0020-7489(02)00008-1).
32. Mr. Paramesha, Mr. Vinay Kumar. G., Mr. Vishakanta Murthy. D.G. A Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Self Instructional Module of Knowledge on Utilization of Emergency Crash Cart System in Hospital among 4th year B.Sc Nursing Students of Selected Nursing Colleges in Mysore *Asian Journal. Nursing Edu. and Research* 6(2) 2016
33. King, R. L. (2004). Nurses' perceptions of their pharmacology educational needs. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 45(4), 392–400. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2648.2003.02922.x>

34. Olasveengen TM, Sunde K, Brunborg C, Thowsen J, Steen PA, Wik L. Intravenous drug administration during out-of-hospital cardiac arrest: a randomized trial. *Jama*. 2009 Nov 25;302(20):2222-9.
35. Rittenberger JC, Bost JE, Menegazzi JJ. Time to give the first medication during resuscitation in out-of-hospital cardiac arrest. *Resuscitation*. 2006 Aug 1;70(2):201-6.
36. Morray JP, Geiduschek JM, Ramamoorthy C, Haberkern CM, Anesthesia-related cardiac arrest in children: initial findings of the Pediatric Perioperative Cardiac Arrest (POCA) Registry. *The Journal of the American Society of Anesthesiologists*. 2000 Jul 1;93(1):6-14.
37. Kripalani S, Goggins K, Nwosu S, Schildcrout J, Medication nonadherence before hospitalization for acute cardiac events. *Journal of health communication*. 2015 Oct 9;20(sup2):34-42.
38. Granfeldt A, Wissenberg M, Hansen SM, Lippert FK, Location of cardiac arrest and impact of pre-arrest chronic disease and medication use on survival. *Resuscitation*. 2017 May 1;114:113-20.
39. Ren X. Cardiac functional medication support. *Chinese Pediatric Emergency Medicine*. 2018:401-6.
40. Chen Y. Clinical Observation of Adrenaline through the Subclavian Vein Cardiac Arrest Rescue Medication. In 2nd International Conference on Civil, Materials and Environmental Sciences 2015 Apr (pp. 531-533). Atlantis Press.
41. Lakshi.R, M. K., & S, M. I. (2015). Assess the knowledge regarding jejunostomy feeding among staff nurses and nursing students in NMCH, nellore. *Journal of Medical Science And Clinical Research*. <https://doi.org/10.18535/jmscr/v3i9.64>
42. Schelbred AB, Nord R. Nurses' experiences of drug administration errors. *J Adv Nurs*. 2007 Nov;60(3):317-24. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2648.2007.04437.x. PMID: 17908127.
43. Lall, S. (2017). The lived experience of making a medication administration error in nursing practice. *International Journal of Nursing*, 4(2). <https://doi.org/10.15640/ijn.v4n2a2>
44. Elsa Sanatombi Devi, Shreemathi S. Mayya Knowledge of cardiac emergency drugs and its application in clinical practice among undergraduate students of a College of Nursing in Karnataka Elsa Sanatombi Devi / *International Journal of Nursing Education*. January-June, 2010, Vol. 2, No. 1
45. Nandasena, G., & Abeysena, C. (2018). Knowledge, attitudes and skills of doctors, nurses and emergency medical technicians in pre-hospital care and emergency medicine who accompany patients in ambulances which arrive at the National Hospital of Sri Lanka. *International Journal of Clinical Anesthesia and Research*, 2(1), 038–043. <https://doi.org/10.29328/journal.ijcar.1001010>
46. N. Tsaloukidis , R. Trifoni , M. Peponi Evaluating Knowledge of Emergency Department Nurses in Recognition and Treatment of Emergency Cardiovascular Events *International Journal Of Health Research and Innovation*, vol.3, no. 1, 2015, 17-27
47. da Silva Oliveira, Elizandra Cassia; de Oliveira, Standardization of drugs in emergency trolleys in intensive care and emergency units. *Revista de EnfermagemReferência* . jul-sep2019, Vol. 4 Issue 22, p97-106. 18p.
48. Li W, An X, Fu M and Li C: Emergency treatment and nursing of children with severe pneumonia complicated by heart failure and respiratory failure: 10 case reports. *Exp Ther Med* 12: 2145-2149, 2016
49. Alves, Thiago Enggle; Silva, Maria Gracirene; Oliveira, Performance Of The Nursing Professional In The Emergency Care To The Users Affected By Acute Myocardial Infarction. *Journal of Nursing UFPE / Revista de EnfermagemUFPE* . Jan2013, Vol. 7 Issue 1, p176-183. 8p.
50. Donoghue AJ, Nadkarni V, Berg RA, Osmond MH, Pediatric Cardiac Arrest Investigators. Out-of-hospital pediatric cardiac arrest: an epidemiologic review and assessment of current knowledge. *Annals of emergency medicine*. 2005 Dec 1;46(6):512-22.
51. Siebert JN, Ehrler F, Combescure C, Lacroix L, mobile device app to reduce time to drug delivery and medication errors during simulated pediatric cardiopulmonary resuscitation: a randomized controlled trial. *Journal of medical Internet research*. 2017 Feb 1;19(2):e7005.
52. Greenberg MI. The use of endotracheal medication in cardiac emergencies. *Resuscitation*. 1984 Nov 1;12(3):155-65.

53. Rojas-Marte G, John J, Sadiq A, Moskovits N, Saunders P, Shani J. Medication-induced Takotsubo Cardiomyopathy presenting with cardiogenic shock—utility of extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO): case report and review of the literature. *Cardiovascular Revascularization Medicine*. 2015 Jan 1;16(1):47-51.
54. Sharma S. K , *Nursing Research & Statistics*, Second Edition (2017), Elsevier publication, Page no: 98,85,116,105,163,168,43,109,251-252,305-306.
55. Denis F Polit, Bernadette P. Hungler, *Nursing Research, Principles & Methods*, 5 th edition, Philadelphia publication, JB Lippincott Company,1995,page no-640-656
56. Denis F Polit, Cheryl Tatano Beck, *Nursing Research Generating & Assessing Evidence for Nursing Practice*, 10th Edition, New Delhi, Wolters Kluwer, India, 2017,page no.748- 750
57. Mr. Rajendra D. Lamkhede Effectiveness of planned teaching programme on knowledge of emergency drugs among staff nurses, *Sinhgad e Journal of Nursing*, Vol. IV, Issue I, June 2014
58. Vinil Upendrababu, Effectiveness of Structured Teaching Programme on knowledge regarding selected Emergency Cardiac Medications among 3rd year B.Sc Nursing Students, *Asian Journal of Nursing Education and Research* Vol. 0804,2018